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SCIENTIFIC AIMS OF NIVB AT THE UNIVERSITY OF CHEMISTRY AND TECHNOLOGY, PRAGUE

ALŽBĚTA DOSTÁLKOVÁ, JITKA VIKTOROVÁ, MATĚJ DANDA, MARKĚTA ČASTORÁLOVÁ, JAN PRCHAL, JAN LIPOV, RADIM NOVOTNÝ, IVANA KRÍŽOVÁ, ANNA KLIMEŠOVÁ, KAROLÍNA ZVONAROVÁ, BARBORA VOKATÁ, LARISA ŠINKOVEC, MARÍNA KAPISHEVA, RICHARD HRABAL, TOMÁŠ RUML, MICHAELA RUMLOVÁ*

*NIVB at the University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Technická 5, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic
michaela.rumlova@vscht.cz*

The NIVB group at the University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, is oriented on several aspects of the replication cycle of selected members of viruses from the Retroviridae, Flaviviridae and Coronaviridae as well as on the multidrug resistant bacteria. Mainly our current research is focused on: (i) the possibility of allosteric modulation of RNA-dependent RNA polymerase SARS-CoV-2; (ii) mechanisms of uncoating within the early phase of retroviral replication cycle and the interactions among viral and host cell proteins (and small molecules) needed by the virus to accomplish this process (iii) lipid membrane binding and RNA packaging process of flaviviral nucleocapsid-like structures formation, and (iv) and determination of antibiotic resistance mechanism in clinical isolates as well as the inhibitors of efflux pumps.

A novel coronavirus Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) emerged in late 2019 in Wuhan China and has caused a global outbreak of acute respiratory disease associated with fatal pneumonia. Due to the proofreading activity of SARS-CoV-2 replication complex (RdRp), the usage of nucleoside analogues as antiviral drugs for COVID-19 treatment is limited. Therefore, we focused on the characterization of RdRp putative allosteric sites and testing of inhibitory activity of compounds binding into these allosteric pockets. We have pre-selected three hydrophobic pockets (Fig. 1) potentially involved in the allosteric regulation of RdRp activity and their characterization by a combination of mutagenesis and activity assay is currently in process. Furthermore, we are interested in *in vitro* analysis of naturally occurring mutations in the RdRp regions, whose occurrence relates to different SARS-CoV2 variants, which have been repeatedly reported in nsp7, nsp8, and nsp12 over the last three years. Another target of our SARS-CoV2 study is the exoribonuclease complex responsible for proofreading activity. The proofreading complex comprises the exoribonuclease domain (nsp14) and its co-factor nsp10. The intervention of proofreading during viral RNA replication is a promising approach to enhance the efficiency of active-site RdRp inhibitors.

Retroviral uncoating is an area of great scientific interest. The recent finding that HIV-1 mature core can enter the nuclear pore of the infected cells has shed new light on this process. By combining cryoEM, MS and iCLIP analysis, we investigate several aspects of the uncoating process, including the core structure and the involvement of host co-factor, for a member of D-type retroviruses, Mason-Pfizer monkey virus (M-PMV). Moreover, we identified a cellular

factor, DEAH-box containing RNA helicase 15 (DHX15), that plays a critical role in M-PMV replication. Its role in both the early and the late phase of the M-PMV replication cycle is currently studied. We also aim to elucidate the relation between the plasma membrane interaction of retroviral polyproteins and regulation of their sequential processing.

Fig. 1. Structure of the SARS-CoV-2 RdRp-RNA complex (PDB ID: 7KRO). Nsp12 (beige) with bound co-factors nsp7 (blue) and nsp8 (purple). The double-strand RNA consists of a template strand (orange) and a newly created strand (green). Predicted allosteric sites are pictured red, with pockets II and III located in the RdRp domain of nsp12 and pocket I found in NiRAN domain.

Flaviviruses such as Dengue virus (DENV), West Nile virus (WNV), Zika virus (ZIKV), Yellow fever virus (YFV), and Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV) are important human pathogens belonging to the arthropod-borne viruses with a worldwide impact on human and animal health. Despite the availability of TBEV vaccine, there is still a need for tick-borne encephalitis treatment. Our research is focused on one of the promising targets for antivirals, a flaviviral capsid (C) protein. The C protein triggers the flaviviral assembly, most probably by simultaneous binding the viral genomic RNA and ER lipid bilayer. Based on our recent publication reporting the NMR structure of TBEV C protein (1), we focused on the identification of the regions/residues of TBEV C involved in lipid-membrane binding and viral genomic RNA interactions. The obtained data should significantly expand our knowledge of the mechanism and specificity of C protein in the process of vRNA packaging during TBEV infection and thus contribute to the development of targeted therapy.

Transmembrane efflux pumps export a wide range of structurally different antibiotics from drug-resistant bacterial cells, thereby reducing intracellular ATB concentration and bacterial sensitivity. Our research in this area is oriented on determination of mechanisms by which clinical isolates acquired their resistance and search for new efflux pumps inhibitors.

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REFERENCE

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